

Original Research Article

Impaired calcium oscillations and PLC ζ dysfunction as key contributors to the low efficiency of ICSI and artificial activation in sheep

Luca Palazzese^a, Domenico Iuso^a, Aurora Scudieri^a, Margherita Moncada^a, Martina Lo Sterzo^a,
 Francesca Boffa^a, Pasqualino Loi^{a,*}, Marta Czernik^{a,1}, Luisa Gioia^{b,1}

^a Department of Veterinary Medicine, University of Teramo, Teramo, 64100, Italy

^b Department of Bioscience and Technology for Food, Agriculture and Environment, University of Teramo, Teramo, 64100, Italy

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ABSTRACT

Intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) is less effective in ovine oocytes than *in vitro* fertilization (IVF), but the reasons remain unclear. Calcium oscillations, driven by phospholipase C zeta 1 (PLC ζ 1), are critical for fertilization success. This study evaluated Ca²⁺ wave dynamics in ovine oocytes matured *in vitro* and fertilized via IVF or ICSI. Metaphase II oocytes were fertilized by IVF (n = 140) or ICSI (n = 105) using frozen-thawed ram spermatozoa. Calcium oscillations were monitored by time-lapse microscopy with Fluo-4 pentapotassium salt, and PLC ζ 1 expression/localization was analysed via immunofluorescence. IVF-fertilized oocytes exhibited prolonged Ca²⁺ oscillations lasting up to 16 h, with peaks persisting during pronuclear formation. ICSI-fertilized oocytes showed restricted Ca²⁺ responses, with peaks limited to the first 4 h. In frozen-thawed sperm, PLC ζ 1 was mainly in the acrosomal region but relocated to the subequatorial region after ionomycin-induced acrosome reaction, mimicking IVF conditions. In contrast, in PVP-treated sperm used for ICSI, PLC ζ 1 mislocalized or was depleted, likely due to premature acrosome loss. These findings indicate that abnormal Ca²⁺ responses underlie ICSI's poor performance in ovine oocytes. Our preliminary results suggest that PLC ζ 1 mislocalization in sperm during ICSI could impair Ca²⁺ signalling. This study, the first to describe Ca²⁺ patterns in sheep oocytes fertilized via IVF, highlights key fertilization failure mechanisms in ICSI and underscores the need to optimize reproductive biotechnologies in farm animals.

1. Introduction

In humans, Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI) has been established as an effective technique for clinical application (Palermo et al., 2017). However, the success of ICSI in farm animals, in particular ruminants, has been limited [1–3]. This is particularly true in sheep, where, although normal lambs derived from ICSI were born over 20 years ago [4,5], the developmental competence of ICSI-derived embryos remains significantly lower than that achieved through *in vitro* fertilization (IVF) [6,7].

Over the years, numerous studies have identified in the failure of artificial oocyte activation (AOA) the primary limiting factor to the success of ICSI in domestic animals [8].

Metaphase II oocytes are activated at fertilization by a series of cytosolic calcium ion (Ca²⁺) oscillations triggered by the sperm-specific protein phospholipase C zeta 1 (PLC ζ 1) [9,10]. To mimic the

physiological signalling of fertilizing sperm, mechanical, electrical, and chemical artificial activation have been employed [11]. While mechanical activation induced by sperm injection has been shown to effectively activate mouse oocytes, this is insufficient in sheep [4]. Chemical activation is the most commonly used method for OA and is particularly essential following ICSI in ruminants, like sheep. This contrasts with other species such as mice, hamsters, rabbits and human, where chemical activation is not necessary [12,13]. Current standard protocols for sheep include chemical activation treatments post-ICSI, often in combination with inhibitors of protein kinases or protein synthesis to enhance activation efficiency [14,15].

Data from other species indicate that the characteristics of these Ca²⁺ oscillations such as amplitude, duration, and frequency, are species-specific and are essential, not limited to oocyte activation alone but also for subsequent embryonic development [16,17]. Notably, the specific pattern of Ca²⁺ transients during fertilization has been shown to

* Corresponding author. Street R. Balzarini 1, Campus Coste S. Agostino, University of Teramo, Teramo (TE), 64100, Italy.

E-mail address: ploi@unite.it (P. Loi).

¹ Co-senior Authorship.

influence early embryogenesis, affecting parameters such as developmental potential [18]. Our previous studies in sheep [19,20] highlighted a significant discrepancy between the post-ICSI activation rate, determined by the formation of two pronuclei (2 PN) (80 %), and the first cleavage rate (35 %), even with optimized OA protocols. DNA staining of presumptive zygotes revealed the presence of 2 PN without apposition or pronuclear envelope breakdown, suggesting that this may be the limiting factor in the developmental competence of ICSI-derived embryos. Given that both early and late events of OA, including PN migration and pronuclear envelope breakdown, are calcium-dependent processes, we hypothesized that the current activation protocols used in sheep effectively induce the initial calcium spike(s), but fail to induce the subsequent crucial ones. This might result in a Ca^{2+} signalling pattern in ICSI-derived oocytes that is markedly different from the physiological one induced by the fertilizing spermatozoon.

This study examines the biological aspects of the ICSI technique in ruminants, focusing on improving its efficiency in sheep. While sperm-induced Ca^{2+} oscillations critical for oocyte activation are well-documented in other mammals [21–23], such studies are lacking for sheep, where ICSI is less effective.

The research investigates Ca^{2+} dynamics in sheep oocytes fertilized via IVF and ICSI, linking alterations to the reduced developmental potential of ICSI-fertilized oocytes, aiming to address this limitation.

2. Results

2.1. Intracellular Ca^{2+} oscillations signal in IVF-fertilized oocytes and its persistence at 2 PN stage

Sheep oocytes fertilized with frozen/thawed semen were

Fig. 1. Detection of Ca^{2+} oscillations in mature sheep oocytes fertilized via IVF and ICSI. (a) Experimental design for the analysis of Ca^{2+} ion intracellular concentration. (b) A representative image showing the fluorescence emitted by fertilized oocytes injected with the calcium probe. Scale bar: 100 μm . (c) Ca^{2+} response in IVF-fertilized oocytes: the left graph shows the response 4–6 h post-fertilization, the central graph represents 8–10 h, and the right graph illustrates the response 12–16 h after fertilization. (d) Ca^{2+} response in ICSI-fertilized oocytes. Sequential monitoring of oocytes subjected to different activation protocols: oocytes fertilized by ICSI without chemical activation; oocytes activated with ionomycin and monitored throughout; oocytes activated with ionomycin and cyclohexamide, observed at 4–8 h post-activation and again at 8–12 h post-activation. In “c–d” the vertical axis represents the normalized as described in Ref. [24] light intensity acquired at 530 nm, while the horizontal axis indicates the various acquisition time points, each spaced 90 s apart.

microinjected with the calcium-sensitive probe Fluo-4 pentapotassium salt at the time of sperm-oocyte fusion (4 h post gamete co-incubation) and immediately subjected to intracellular Ca^{2+} analysis. Time-lapse recordings revealed a distinct pattern of Ca^{2+} release (Video 1). Responding oocytes (44.3 %, $n = 140$) exhibited continuous Ca^{2+} oscillations starting immediately after sperm-oocyte fusion and persisting until 12–16 h post-IVF (Fig. 1a–c) when the formation of the male and female pronucleus has occurred (Fig. 3g). Individual Ca^{2+} peaks lasted an average of 4.5 min, with peak amplitude and frequency varying significantly (Fig. 2a and b). The highest amplitude was observed at 8–10 h post-IVF (1.844 A.U.), compared to 4–6 h (1.389 A.U.) and 12–16 h post-IVF (1.382 A.U.), $P < 0.001$ (Fig. 2c). Sham-injected oocytes (microinjection of Fluo-4, without IVF) did not show any Ca^{2+} oscillations (data not shown), demonstrating that the probe injection itself did not have an impact on Ca^{2+} response.

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2.2. Chemical activation of ICSI-fertilized oocytes does not reflect the Ca^{2+} oscillations of IVF-fertilized oocytes

A total of 105 oocytes were fertilized via ICSI and analysed for Ca^{2+} response. As an initial step, oocytes fertilized by ICSI with frozen/thawed semen, without post-ICSI chemical activation, were analysed. No Ca^{2+} peaks were observed from 0 to 4 h (Fig. 1d).

Differently, a Ca^{2+} response was detected in ICSI-fertilized oocytes after chemical activation, although it was markedly different from that observed in IVF oocytes. Notably, after ionomycin treatment, as well as after a combined ionomycin and cycloheximide treatment, the duration

of Ca^{2+} response was just over an hour (approximately 1 h and 20 min, and 1 h and 25 min, respectively), then no other significant Ca^{2+} increase was observed in the rest of the analysis (Fig. 1d). In particular, when analysed the average peak frequency (peaks/hour) at various post-fertilization intervals (Fig. 2b and c), in the first period (4–6 h) post-fertilization, IVF oocytes exhibited an average frequency of 4.8 peaks/hour, compared to 4 peaks/hour in chemically activated-ICSI oocytes. Significant differences were observed during the following hours. At 8–10 h post-fertilization the frequency in IVF oocytes increased to 8.2 peaks/hour, while no peaks were detected in chemically activated-ICSI oocytes ($P < 0.0001$). Similarly, during the 12–16-h interval, IVF oocytes maintained a frequency of 4 peaks/hour, whereas no peaks were observed in chemically activated-ICSI oocytes ($P < 0.0001$). Concerning the mean amplitude of the Ca^{2+} peaks observed in ICSI-fertilized oocytes during the first 4 h after activation, it was significantly higher in combined ionomycin/cycloheximide group (0.958 A.U.) than in ionomycin group (0.849 A.U., $P = 0.0391$) (Fig. 2c).

Sham-injected oocytes (ICSI without sperm microinjection) did not show any Ca^{2+} oscillations, demonstrating that the sperm injection procedure itself did not have an impact on Ca^{2+} response.

2.3. Reduced parental pronuclei dimension in ICSI-derived zygotes

Since ICSI-induced Ca^{2+} response was not equivalent to that initiated by IVF, we examined the next stages of the fertilization process in the two groups.

In vitro matured sheep oocytes displayed similar rates of two-pronuclei (2 PN) stage, regardless of the fertilization method, with 71 % (9/13) of IVF-fertilized oocytes and 77 % (9/12) of ICSI-fertilized

Fig. 2. Frequency and duration of Ca^{2+} peaks. (a) Individual traces of oocytes fertilized via IVF. (b) Mean frequency of Ca^{2+} peaks monitored in the two groups IVF and ICSI. * means $P < 0.001$. (c) Comparisons of mean peak amplitudes in IVF (graph on the left) and ICSI (graph on the right). **** means $P < 0.0001$. * means $P = 0.0391$.

Fig. 3. Embryonic development of oocytes fertilized by IVF and ICSI and quantification of embryo formation at the 2 pronuclei (2 PN) stage. (a) Schematic representation illustrating that, regardless of whether fertilization occurs via IVF or ICSI, oocytes exhibit a similar rate of 2 PN embryo formation at 14 h post-fertilization. However, by 24 h, oocytes fertilized via ICSI experience a marked developmental arrest. (b) Embryonic development, * indicates $P = 0.0150$, **** indicates $P < 0.0001$. (c, d) Representative images of embryos 24 h post-fertilization showing first cleavage or developmental arrest: (c) immunocytochemistry, α -tubulin in green and DAPI in blue showing an oocyte halted in anaphase II with an uncondensed spermatozoa head (spz head), and (d) embryos at the 2-cell stage. Scale bar: 50 μm in “c” and 100 μm in “d”. (e) Measurement of the radius of female and male pronuclei (female PN and male PN, respectively) in embryos fertilized via IVF and ICSI, analysed 14 h post-fertilization. *** indicates $P = 0.0009$; ** indicates $P = 0.003$. (f) Quantification of the volume of female and male PN starting from the measurement of their relative radius. Embryos were analysed at 14 h post IVF and ICSI. ** in IVF and ICSI female PN indicates $P = 0.0011$, ** in IVF and ICSI male PN indicates $P = 0.0049$. (g) Representative images of IVF and ICSI embryos assessed for the 2 PN stage 14 h post-fertilization, showing DAPI-stained nuclei (blue) and α -tubulin (green). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

oocytes achieving 2 PN formation (Fig. 3a and b). However, a significant difference was observed in the first cleavage rates 24 h post-fertilization. Oocytes fertilized by ICSI showed a marked reduction in cleavage (33 %, 23/71) compared to those fertilized by IVF (66 %, 54/82), with statistical significance ($P = 0.0150$), furthermore, the formation of blastocysts on day 7 was also lower (20 %, 14/71 – ICSI; 62 %, 51/82 – IVF, $P < 0.001$), (Fig. 3b–d). The findings highlight a compromise in the migration and apposition of parental pronuclei in embryos fertilized via ICSI.

This disparity in developmental progression was further reflected in the size of the parental pronuclei. At 14 h post-fertilization, both the female and male pronuclei in IVF-fertilized oocytes were significantly larger than those in ICSI-fertilized oocytes. Specifically, the radius of the female pronucleus was larger in IVF embryos (11.77 μm , $n = 9$) compared to ICSI embryos (8.62 μm , $n = 9$; $P = 0.0009$) (Fig. 3e), and similarly, the male pronucleus radius in IVF embryos was also greater (13.68 μm , $n = 9$) than in ICSI embryos (9.94 μm , $n = 9$; $P = 0.003$)

(Fig. 3e–g). To provide a more comprehensive assessment, the volume of the individual pronuclei was calculated based on the radius measurements. These volume measurements corroborated the observed differences in pronuclear size. The average volume of the female pronucleus was significantly larger in IVF embryos ($5.7 \times 10^3 \mu\text{m}^3$, $n = 9$) compared to ICSI embryos ($2.7 \times 10^3 \mu\text{m}^3$, $n = 9$; $P = 0.0011$) (Fig. 3f). Similarly, the male pronucleus volume in IVF embryos was larger ($1.07 \times 10^4 \mu\text{m}^3$, $n = 9$) than that in ICSI embryos ($4.8 \times 10^3 \mu\text{m}^3$, $n = 9$; $P = 0.0049$) (Fig. 3f).

2.4. ICSI procedure induces acrosome degradation and alters PLC ζ 1 localization in spermatozoa

To investigate the potential causes of the abnormal Ca^{2+} oscillations in oocytes fertilized via ICSI, we analysed spermatozoa dynamics during the IVF and ICSI procedures, focusing on acrosome reaction and PLC ζ 1

localization.

FITC-PNA assay revealed a key difference in the acrosome reaction among the groups. Both the ionomycin treatment (IONO), which was used to induce the acrosome reaction in capacitated sperm, and the exposure of semen to 12 % PVP, which was used to simulate the ICSI conditions, resulted in acrosome degradation. In PVP group, a highest proportion (100 %, $n = 200$) was observed than in the IONO group (83.3 %, $n = 211$), while no acrosome degradation was detected in the CTR group (0 %, $n = 170$). Statistical analysis revealed that the PVP group had a significantly higher rate of acrosome degradation compared to the IONO group ($P < 0.001$) and the CTR group ($P = 0.0426$) (Fig. 4a and b).

Regarding the localization of PLC ζ 1 in the spermatozoa, two distinct patterns were observed by immunofluorescence analysis: acrosomal and subequatorial, along with cases where PLC ζ 1 was absent (Fig. 4a). The distribution of PLC ζ 1 varied significantly between the experimental groups. Spermatozoa in the CTR group displayed the highest prevalence of acrosomal localization ($P < 0.001$), with 86.2 % ($n = 163$) of sperm exhibiting this pattern, compared to 9.5 % ($n = 185$) in the IONO group and 28 % ($n = 171$) in the PVP group (Fig. 4c). Regarding the localization of PLC ζ 1 in the subequatorial position, the IONO group displayed the highest proportion of spermatozoa exhibiting this pattern. Specifically, 41.4 % of sperm in the IONO group showed PLC ζ 1 in the subequatorial position, compared to 21.3 % in the PVP group and only 6.7 % in the CTR group. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences between the IONO and PVP groups ($P = 0.0141$), as well as between the

IONO and CTR groups ($P < 0.0001$) (Fig. 4c and d). The absence of PLC ζ 1 was frequently observed in PVP and IONO groups, with 50.7 % and 49.1 %, respectively, of spermatozoa lacking detectable PLC ζ 1 (Fig. 4c and d). These percentages were significantly higher compared to the CTR group ($P < 0.0001$), where only 7.1 % of sperm showed absence of PLC ζ 1.

3. Discussion

The results of this study provide new insights into the dynamics of calcium ions (Ca^{2+}) signalling in farm animals. A normal dynamic of Ca^{2+} release into the oocyte cytoplasm following fertilization is essential for oocyte activation, but also for driving subsequent multiple and precise processes that are essential to early embryonic development [25–27]. The reported literature highlights a significant gap in the understanding of Ca^{2+} patterns in oocytes of farm animals, particularly over the past decade. While Ca^{2+} dynamics are well described in laboratory models [24], studies monitoring these patterns in farm animals' oocytes fertilized by ICSI or IVF are nearly absent. Our study shows that 2 PN embryos obtained through ICSI, although produced in numbers comparable to those from IVF, exhibit a reduced dimension of the male pronucleus compared to those in IVF embryos.

The Ca^{2+} deficit within the ooplasm selectively affects the male pronucleus, consistent with studies linking fertilization events to sperm nucleus dynamics and sperm chromatin abnormalities with pre-implantation defects. Reviews highlight asymmetric parental

Fig. 4. PLC ζ 1 and acrosome dynamics during IVF and ICSI procedures. (a) Representative image showing the different localizations of PLC ζ 1 (in red) and acrosome integrity (FITC-PNA - in green). Top row: spermatozoa with intact acrosome and PLC ζ 1 in the acrosomal position. Bottom row: spermatozoa with degraded acrosome and PLC ζ 1 expressed in subequatorial position. Scale bar: 5 μ m. (b) Graph depicting the rate of acrosome integrity across different treatment groups: control (CTR), representing frozen/thawed semen; ionomycin-induced acrosome reaction after 5 min (IONO); and semen incubated for 30 min in PVP (PVP). **** indicates $P < 0.0001$, * indicates $P = 0.0426$. (c) Position of PLC ζ 1 in the CTR, IONO and PVP groups. **** indicates $P < 0.0001$, * in "IONO acrosomal" vs "PVP acrosomal" indicates $P = 0.0192$, * in "IONO subequatorial" vs "PVP subequatorial" indicates $P = 0.0141$. (d) Representative images illustrating the acrosome integrity and PLC ζ 1 localization patterns in CTR and PVP-treated spermatozoa. Scale bars: 10 μ m (top row) and 25 μ m (bottom row). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

chromatin dynamics and epigenetic remodeling in the shift from pluripotency to totipotency [28,29]. Time-lapse analyses have revealed marked asymmetry in pronuclear dynamics and chromatin organization, emphasizing that embryo developmental fate depends heavily on fertilization events [30]. Indeed, we have demonstrated a strong G2-S block in sheep zygotes too, as a consequence of massive DNA damage [31]. Moreover, it is well-established that ICSI-derived embryos undergo distinct chromatin remodeling in the parental pronuclei compared to IVF embryos, with these differences being attributed to chromatin dynamics rather than variations in chromosome number at this post-fertilization stage [32]. This mechanism may contribute to the lower efficiency of live births following ICSI in ruminants compared to other species like horses, mice, and humans.

The formation of pronuclei in mammalian oocytes is critically dependent on the modulation of intracellular calcium oscillations. Studies on electrically activated murine oocytes [33,34] have demonstrated that the amplitude, frequency, and duration of calcium spikes are key determinants of the success and timing of pronuclear development. Adequate repetitive calcium stimulation is essential for completing meiosis and forming pronuclei, while suboptimal conditions result in incomplete activation or meiotic arrest at metaphase. The embryonic development data indicate a block at the pronuclear migration phase, as the rate of parental pronuclei formation is consistent between the two groups. However, ICSI embryos exhibit a significant reduction in the first mitotic division. It is well-established that zygotes face a stringent block between the G2-S phases [31] and that the cytoskeleton plays a crucial role in pronuclear migration [35]. Furthermore, calcium is known to be essential in membrane fusion [36,37]. Focus should therefore be directed toward the functional role of Ca^{2+} during this critical window of embryonic development. Considering the data, which exclude impairments in earlier stages and clearly show a block in the first embryonic cleavage, it is highly plausible that the key factor lies in pronuclear migration and apposition.

In mammals, the entry of the spermatozoon into the oocyte cytoplasm triggers an extensive series of Ca^{2+} transients, which cease near the formation of the pronuclei, suggesting a close relationship between Ca^{2+} oscillations and pronuclear formation [38].

Ca^{2+} oscillations are induced by phospholipase ζ (PLC ζ), a sperm-specific isoform of phospholipase C that hydrolyzes phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate (PIP2) to produce inositol-1,4,5-triphosphate (IP3) [9,39]. However, specific information on its subcellular localization within bovine spermatozoa remains limited and warrants further investigation [38,40,41]. In porcine spermatozoa, PLC ζ is localized primarily in the acrosomal and post-acrosomal regions of the sperm head, with additional distribution in the tail, a pattern that underscores its potential role in triggering oocyte activation [42]. However, the expression of PLC ζ in the tail was confirmed to be a nonspecific signal, and in any case, the injection of the sperm tail alone into the oocyte was insufficient to activate it [42]. Similarly, in equine spermatozoa, PLC ζ has been detected in the acrosomal, equatorial, and post-acrosomal regions of the head and along the principal piece of the flagellum [43]. In humans, PLC ζ shows a comparable localization pattern, being present in the acrosomal, equatorial, and post-acrosomal regions of the sperm head. However, inter-individual variability in the expression and localization of PLC ζ has been observed, which may influence male fertility [44].

For sheep, while PLC ζ is presumed to play a similar role, as happens in other mammals, specific studies detailing its localization in ovine spermatozoa are currently lacking. Our results demonstrate the expression of PLC ζ 1 protein in ram spermatozoa and, interestingly, indicate that treating spermatozoa with PVP, a condition commonly used in the ICSI procedure, results in an abnormal redistribution of the protein. Before any treatments (CTR group), PLC ζ 1 is predominantly (more than 86 %) localized in the acrosomal region of the sperm cell. Differently, in nearly half of the ionomycin-treated spermatozoa, which undergo acrosome reaction after capacitation, mimicking the

physiological conditions occurring during gamete interaction at fertilization, PLC ζ 1 is localized in the subequatorial position presumably translocating from acrosomal region during the process of capacitation. It is noteworthy that in spermatozoa incubated in PVP, which lose the acrosome too, only a significantly lower percentage of sperm showed the correct subequatorial PLC ζ 1 localization. We could hypothesize that spermatozoa incubated in PVP undergo the loss of the acrosome in a non-physiological way, thus lacking the necessary space-time molecular reorganization occurring before acrosome reaction and subsequent sperm-oocyte fusion. Given the crucial role of PLC ζ in Ca^{2+} release following fertilization, as previously described, these findings might be responsible for the different pattern of Ca^{2+} oscillations observed in IVF and ICSI oocytes after fertilization. However, it is worth nothing that data on calcium release patterns after fertilization in ovine oocytes are entirely missing. This study documented that for the first time the Ca^{2+} pattern elicited by the sperm in IVF sheep oocytes is detectable and assessable up to 16 h after fertilization. Interestingly, the Ca^{2+} pattern observed in oocytes fertilized by ICSI is markedly different. ICSI alone, without chemical activation, did not produce any calcium peaks; calcium oscillations were only detected when chemical activation was applied, although the pattern was markedly defective comparing to the long-lasting oscillatory response observed in IVF oocytes. Considering the results of PLC ζ 1 analysis, we could suppose that the loss of the protein from spermatozoa due to the PVP treatment is the reason why no Ca^{2+} peaks are observed without artificial activation post-ICSI. This indication is further supported by our previous studies, where the use of only selected motile spermatozoa, ensuring the retention of PLC ζ 1, successfully induced oocyte activation [45]. Our preliminary findings do not allow us to define the precise significance of this different frequency of oscillations. However, in light of previous studies [18], we might hypothesize that the spatiotemporal distribution of Ca^{2+} peaks could have specific effects on various post-fertilization events or late activation events, namely pronuclear migration and apposition.

Both chemical activation treatments (ionomycin and ionomycin combined with cycloheximide) induced calcium Ca^{2+} responses, although the pattern was abnormal compared to that of IVF, consisting in few Ca^{2+} spikes that elapsed in a very short period. Even if oocyte chemical activation is successful, this atypical Ca^{2+} profile may have detrimental effects on late event of oocyte activation and the subsequent first cleavage, so impairing embryonic development. The importance of a correct calcium signalling after *in vitro* fertilization, close to the physiological one, and proper pronuclear development has been widely demonstrated. Evidences demonstrated that insufficient Ca^{2+} oscillations can hinder the embryo's ability to implant, while an exaggerated Ca^{2+} response can impair development after implantation [18]. In mouse IVF oocytes, blocking pronucleus formation reduces the activity of Cdk1-cyclin B and MAP kinases, showing that nuclear events regulate cell cycle kinases. Persistent Ca^{2+} oscillations, even when these kinases are low, suggest that pronucleus formation and nuclear transport control the timing of Ca^{2+} oscillations during fertilization. The smaller pronuclei in ICSI embryos compared to IVF embryos may result from Ca^{2+} regulating pronucleus formation by stopping fertilization-induced oscillations. The nuclear membrane becomes permeable before the main Ca^{2+} rise, indicating that nuclear envelope breakdown (NEBD) is essential to trigger the Ca^{2+} transients needed for cell division [38].

Additional experiments involving microinjection of PLC ζ 1 mRNA or protein are necessary to provide further evidence in the sheep model to confirm the role of PLC ζ 1 in triggering Ca^{2+} oscillations. Moreover, it remains crucial to elucidate the molecular Ca^{2+} -dependent mechanism induced by PLC ζ 1, particularly the pronuclear development that drives embryo development progression. However, our findings provide initial insights into the causes behind the poor development outcomes in ICSI-fertilized farm animal oocytes and suggest potential avenues to overcome it. Specifically, the use of activation protocols and subsequent culture conditions that mimic prolonged Ca^{2+} spikes could represent a strategy to rescue oocytes fertilized via ICSI.

4. Materials and methods

4.1. Institutional animal care and use committee (IACUC) approval

The animal experiment (semen collection) has been approved by the Italian Ministry of Health (No. 200/2017-PR) based on the research description prepared by the ethics committee of the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale di Teramo (Prot. 944F0.1 del November 04, 2016). All methods were performed following the relevant guidelines and regulations of the Italian Minister of Health.

4.2. Chemicals

All materials were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), unless specified otherwise.

4.3. Semen collection

Semen from a fertile Sardinian ram, whose reproductive capacity has been previously validated, was collected following the established protocol [46]. In brief, the collection involved the use of an artificial vagina filled with warm water (40–44 °C), connected to a 15-mL sterile tube. Sperm motility was promptly assessed using a stereomicroscope immediately after collection. The sample was diluted 1:1 with Basic Medium (300 mM TRIS base, 105 mM citric acid, 82 mM fructose, 150,000 IU penicillin G, 2 mM streptomycin in 67.2 mL bi-distilled water) and transported to the laboratory in a transportable incubator (INC-RB1 Biotherm, Cryologic, Blackburn, Australia) at 32–35 °C.

4.4. Semen cryopreservation

Semen cryopreservation was carried out in accordance with the established protocol outlined by Ref. [20]. To summarize, the freezing medium was prepared as follows: a Basic Medium was formulated by dissolving 2.42 g of TRIS base, 1.36 g of citric acid, 1.00 g of fructose, 100,000 I.U. of penicillin G, and 0.1 g of streptomycin in 67.20 mL of bi-distilled water, with the pH adjusted to a range of 6.7–6.8. Next, the Basic Medium was divided into two equal volumes, resulting in Medium A (maintained at 30 °C) and Medium B (kept at 4 °C). Medium A contained 20 % egg yolk and 12.8 % ddH₂O, while Medium B contained 20 % egg yolk and 12.8 % glycerol. An equal volume of each of these two mediums was added to the ejaculate, achieving a final concentration of 400 × 10⁶ spermatozoa/mL. The process involved adding Medium A (at 30 °C) to the ejaculate, which was then maintained at 4 °C for a duration of 2 h. Subsequently, Medium B (at 4 °C) was introduced and maintained for an additional 2 h at the same temperature. Throughout this process, tubes were agitated every 30 min. Finally, 250 µL straws were filled with the semen and allowed to equilibrate on liquid nitrogen vapours for 20 min. Following this, the straws were sealed and immediately submerged in liquid nitrogen.

4.5. Cumulus-oocyte complexes recovery and *in vitro* maturation (IVM)

Sheep ovaries were harvested from a local slaughterhouse and promptly transported to the laboratory at 37 °C within a 2-h window from the time of slaughter. Cumulus-oocyte complexes (COCs) were aspirated using 21G needles in the presence of 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-piperazineethanesulfonic acid (HEPES)-buffered TCM-199 medium (H199; Gibco, Life Technologies, Milan, Italy) supplemented with 0.005 % (w/v) heparin. Only COCs exhibiting a minimum of two layers of compact cumulus cells were chosen for subsequent *In Vitro* Maturation (IVM). In 4-well dishes, 500 µL of IVM medium [bicarbonate-buffered TCM-199 (Gibco) containing 2 mM glutamine, 0.3 mM sodium pyruvate, 100 µM cysteamine, 10 % (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS; Gibco), 5 µg/mL follicle-stimulating hormone (Ovagen, ICP, Auckland, New Zealand), 5 µg/mL luteinizing hormone, and 1 µg/mL 17 β-estradiol] was

added to each well. Oocyte maturation was performed in a humidified atmosphere at 38.5 °C and 5 % CO₂ in air for 24 h, as previously described [47].

4.6. *In vitro* fertilization (IVF)

In vitro fertilization (IVF) was performed as previously described [48]. Briefly, 24 h post IVM, COCs were examined under a stereomicroscope, and only those displaying an expansion of cumulus cells were chosen for IVF. Subsequently, COCs were rapidly pipetted into a 300 U/ml hyaluronidase solution (dissolved in TCM-199), subjected to two washes in H199, and then placed into 50 µL drops (in groups of 8–10 oocytes per drop) of IVF medium [SOF- with 20 % oestrus sheep serum (v/v) and 16 mM isoproterenol], each covered by mineral oil (Mineral Oil, cat. 51002; ivf Bioscience). A single straw of frozen semen, containing 100 × 10⁶ spermatozoa, was rapidly thawed in 35 °C water and subsequently centrifuged in a sperm-wash medium [bicarbonate-buffered Synthetic Oviductal Fluid (SOF), with 0.4 % (w/v) fatty-acid-free BSA] at 1200 rpm for 5 min. The supernatant was carefully discarded, and 5 × 10⁶ spermatozoa were then introduced into each drop. The drops were incubated in a humidified atmosphere at 38.5 °C, 5 % CO₂, and 7 % O₂. After a 4-h incubation period, the oocytes were carefully pipetted into SOF- medium to eliminate the majority of spermatozoa adhered to the zona pellucida. Following IVF, the oocytes were either utilized in the experiments or transferred to *in vitro* embryonic culture, as elaborated in the subsequent paragraphs.

4.7. Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI) and oocyte chemical activation

In order to focus the analyses only on the effects of the fertilization technique, the same pools of IVM oocytes and frozen-thawed ram semen were used for IVF and Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection (ICSI), which were performed as follows.

The ICSI procedure was conducted following the methodology previously delineated [46]. Cumulus-Oocyte Complexes (COCs) underwent processing, as detailed in the preceding section on IVF, aimed at the removal of cumulus cells. In summary, a single straw was rapidly thawed by brief immersion in 35 °C water, opened, and transferred using a 1.5 mL Eppendorf pipette. Subsequently, it was incubated for 3 min in a humidified atmosphere at 38.5 °C and 5 % CO₂. Following this, 5 µL of semen was mixed with 100 µL of IVF-medium buffered with HEPES, referred to as H-IVF medium. As previously tested and demonstrated [45], this mixture was then further diluted in a 1:1 ratio with 12 % (w:v) PolyVinylPyrrolidone (PVP). A 10 µL drop of this diluted mixture was carefully placed on the lid of a Petri dish positioned on a warmed microscope stage, all covered with mineral oil.

Fertilization procedures were conducted using an inverted microscope (Eclipse Ti2-U, Nikon) coupled with a micromanipulation system (NT-88NEN, Narishige, Tokyo, Japan) and a piezo-driven micropipette system (PiezoXpert, Eppendorf, Milan, Italy). Oocyte injection took place 24 h after the initiation of IVM. Drops containing PVP and sperm were replenished every 10 oocytes injected. Post-injection, oocytes underwent chemical OA through a 5-min incubation in 5 µM ionomycin in H199 + 0.4 % BSA, followed by a 5-min wash in H199 + 0.4 % BSA. Subsequently, they were placed in IVC-Medium (BO-IVC, cat. 71005; ivf, Bioscience, Falmouth, UK) supplemented with 10 µg/mL cycloheximide and incubated for 3.5 h in a humidified atmosphere at 38.5 °C and 5 % CO₂.

To determine whether or not the sperm injection procedure itself had an impact on fertilization-induced Ca²⁺ oscillations, a group of MII oocytes was identically treated but sham-injected (control ICSI), then immediately analysed in time lapse to detect the Ca²⁺ response.

4.8. Time lapse analyses and imaging of Ca^{2+} pattern in oocytes fertilized via IVF and ICSI

Following fertilization (IVF or ICSI), a qualitative analysis of Ca^{2+} dynamics was performed using a Ca^{2+} sensitive probe. Oocytes were microinjected with Fluo-4 (Fluo-4 pentapotassium salt, Invitrogen, F14200; injected volume: 30–40 μ L), dissolved in microinjection buffer (100 mM KCl, 20 mM HEPES, pH 7.2) as described by Swann and collaborators [27]. Microinjections were carried out under an inverted microscope (Eclipse Ti2-U, Nikon) equipped with a micromanipulation system (NT-88NEN, Narishige, Tokyo, Japan). After 40 min in incubator for the recovery from injection, a number of 12 oocytes per trail were placed on a sterile chambered cover glass, in a 50 μ L drop of 0.5 % agar (w:v) covered with 1 mL of IVC-Medium (BO-IVC, cat. 71005; ivf Bioscience), and analysed in time lapse microscopy (Nikon A1r, Tokyo, Japan) in optimized condition (38.5 °C, 5 % CO_2 , in humidified atmosphere).

Ca^{2+} recordings were carried out using a 488-nm line excitation of an air-cooled 100 mW argon laser (Spectra-Physics), at 20X magnification, with a delay of acquisition of 1.5–6 min. Recordings were performed starting from the time of sperm-oocyte fusion (4 h after gamete co-incubation or immediately after sperm injection/OA) [48] and for the duration of the first cell cycle. Data were analysed using the NIS ELEMENTS 4.40 program. The Ca^{2+} response traces were analysed using GraphPad and Excel software by normalizing each individual oocyte tracing to the mean value of the traces (F/F_{mean}).

4.9. *In vitro* embryo culture (IVC)

An aliquot of the oocytes fertilized through IVF and ICSI were directly placed into the *in vitro* embryo culture, which followed our standard laboratory procedure [47] with slight modifications. In brief, all presumptive zygotes were cultured in groups of five within a 20- μ L drop of IVC-Medium (BO-IVC, cat. 71005; ivf Bioscience), covered with mineral oil (Mineral Oil, cat. 51002; ivf Bioscience), and maintained in a humidified atmosphere at 38.5 °C with 5 % CO_2 and 7 % O_2 . *In vitro* development was assessed 24 h after fertilization/OA for cleavage, considering only 2-cell embryos as having cleaved. Embryo observation and image acquisition were conducted using an inverted microscope (Eclipse Ti2-U; Nikon) equipped with Octax EyeWare Imaging Software (version 2.3.0.372; Vitrolife, Västra Frölunda, Sweden).

4.10. Parental pronuclei detection and immunofluorescence of α -tubulin

Presumptive zygotes were fixed at 14 h post-fertilization or post-OA for IVF-derived embryos and ICSI-derived embryos, respectively. First, zygotes were treated with acid Tyrode's solution (pH 2.4) for 30 s followed by 30 s incubation in 0.5 % Pronase to dissolve the zona pellucida. The zone free zygotes were then fixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA) in PHEM buffer (60 mM PIPES, 25 mM HEPES, 10 mM EGTA, 4 mM $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, pH 6.9) for 20 min. Following the washes in PBS with 0.4 % PVP, they were next permeabilized for 15 min with 0.5 % Triton X-100 in PHEM. After four washes (5 min each) in PHEM with 0.05 % Tween20, zygotes were blocked in 1 % BSA in PHEM with 100 mM glycine at room temperature for 1 h. Zygotes were then incubated with anti- α -Tubulin primary antibody (ab7291, Abcam) diluted 1:200 in 1 % BSA/PHEM with 100 mM glycine, overnight at 4 °C. The next day, after four washes in PHEM with 0.05 % Tween 20, the samples were incubated with Alexa Fluor 488 goat anti-mouse (A11001, Invitrogen) diluted 1:200 in 1 % BSA/PHEM with 100 mM glycine for 45 min at room temperature. Nuclei were counterstained for 5 min in 1 mg DAPI in 10 mL of PBS at room temperature. The images were captured using a confocal microscope (Nikon A1r, Tokyo, Japan).

4.11. Acrosomal membrane integrity

For all sperm analyses, only frozen-thawed ram spermatozoa were used as fresh spermatozoa are not used in standard routine procedures of *in vitro* fertilization (IVF and ICSI). Each thawed paillette containing the spermatozoa was divided into three parts in order to have the following sperm conditions: untreated (CTR), acrosome reaction-induced (ionomycin-treated), and PVP-treated. Fluorescein isothiocyanate-conjugated peanut agglutinin (FITC-PNA) assay was carried out on spermatozoa to assess the acrosomal status. Following the washing, a smear was prepared using 10 μ L of the semen suspension. The slides were air-dried at RT for 5 min, fixed in 100 % ethanol for 5 min, and subsequently washed 2–3 times in clean PBS. Staining was performed with 200 μ L of PNA:DAPI (1:1) solution (PNA: 40 mg/mL, DAPI: 0.5 μ g/mL, both in dissolved in PBS) for 12 min at RT in the dark. After staining, the slides were briefly washed 2–3 times in bi-distilled water, mounted with Fluoromount aqueous mounting medium (SLCN3571), and analysed under a confocal microscope (Nikon Eclipse Ti-E, software: NIS-Elements Confocal).

4.12. Detection and localization of PLC ζ 1 protein by immunofluorescence

The presence and localization of PLC ζ 1 was detected in the spermatozoa of the three groups by immunofluorescence.

Following fixation in paraformaldehyde, the samples were smear-swiped on poly-L-lysine-treated slides, air-dried for about 30 min and permeabilized with 0.5 % Triton X-100 in PBS for 30 min. The slides were then washed twice with 0.05 % Tween20 in PBS (PBST), and the nonspecific binding sites were blocked using 3 % BSA in PBS for 1 h at room temperature. Samples were then incubated overnight at 4 °C with anti-PLC ζ 1 antibody (1.5 mg/mL; Thermofisher; PA5-98556) in a humid chamber, while negative controls were incubated in the absence of primary antibody. The next day, after washing twice with PBST, the samples were incubated with a goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody conjugated to Alexa Fluor 546 (1:800; Thermofisher Scientific, USA; A11010) for 1 h. The slides were then stained with FITC-PNA (40 μ g/mL) and Hoechst-33342 (1 μ g/mL) for 15 min at RT in the dark. Slides with spermatozoa were mounted with Fluoromount aqueous mounting medium. Fluorescent images were acquired using a laser-scanning confocal microscope (Nikon A1r, Tokyo, Japan).

4.13. Statistical analysis

Comparisons for statistical significance of experimental values between treatments and experiments were performed in three or more experiments performed on different batches of oocytes and spermatozoa in most studies. Prism-GraphPad software (Version 6.01, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA) was used to perform the statistical comparisons that include unpaired Student's t-tests, Fisher's exact test, and one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons, as applicable, and the production of graphs to display the data. All data are presented as mean \pm SD. Differences were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Luca Palazzese: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Domenico Iuso:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Aurora Scudieri:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Margherita Moncada:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Martina Lo Sterzo:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Francesca Boffa:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Pasqualino Loi:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Marta Czernik:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Luisa Gioia:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis,

Conceptualization.

Data availability statement

All the data will be made available to the editors of the journal for review or upon request.

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Declaration of competing interest

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